

Exploring the pre sowing techniques for enhancing the germination of small onion (*Allium cepa* var. *aggregatum*) seeds var. Co (On) – 6

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Abstract

The present study was conducted to assess the presowing seed treatment using GA₃ in small onion seeds var. Co (On) 6 in the Department of Vegetable Science, TNAU, Coimbatore during September 2023. Seeds were soaked in GA₃ at 100ppm for 12hrs, 18hrs, 24hrs and water along with control in completely Randomized Design (CRD) with four replications respectively. Germination percentage, seedling length, dry weight and seedling vigour index was improved significantly in onion at 100ppm of GA₃ for 12hrs over control. The variety Co (On) 6 can be beneficial for the farmer as its germination percentage and vigour is good it may be grown in farmer field for the establishment so that they improve the productivity and increase the economic benefit to the farmer.

Keywords: Onion, GA₃, seeds, germination, farmer

Introduction

Onions, a crucial and adaptable vegetable found in culinary traditions worldwide alongside tomatoes, belong to the Alliaceae family with 16 chromosomes. They are extensively cultivated across various climates and soil types globally. India holds the second position in both area and production (after China) and ranks third in exports (following the Netherlands and Spain). The onion cultivation area is reported to be 1.91 million hectares with a production of 31.27 million metric tons. India has exported 2.5 million metric tons of fresh onions globally, valued at Rs. 45.2279 billion (APEDA, 2022). Known as the 'queen of the kitchen' for its distinctive flavor and aroma, onions contain allyl propyl disulphide, a volatile oil responsible for their pungent taste.

Onions can be propagated through both seeds and bulbs. Using seeds can improve the benefit-cost ratio, unlike the bulb-to-bulb method, which can lead to a decline in quality and yield over time. Continuous use of bulbs may result in lower quality bulbs and reduced yield, leading to higher production costs and a decrease in plant population, thereby diminishing the economic benefits for farmers (Kaur *et al.*, 2017). However, onion seeds often have a minimum germination percentage (around 70%), limited longevity, and viability, resulting in poor seedling establishment in nurseries. High-quality seedlings can enhance establishment rates in the field and ultimately boost productivity (Thoriqussalam and Damanhuri, 2019). The quality of onion seeds is influenced by various factors such as the growing environment, seed development conditions, location on the plant, harvesting methods, storage conditions, and seed treatment prior to sowing. Seed priming is a promising method to improve seedling establishment, particularly when seed size is small and seed establishment is poor.

As per Khan (1992), seed priming involves a controlled hydration treatment that stimulates the physiological and biochemical activities of seeds while inhibiting radical protrusion. This process entails soaking seeds in water, osmotic solutions, growth regulators, or a combination thereof, followed by drying to prevent radical emergence. Seed priming promotes uniform germination and growth. The application of plant growth regulators (PGRs) during seed germination is fundamental to plant growth (Miransari and Smith, 2014). Among these regulators, GA₃ is crucial for seed germination as it stimulates cell division (Wen *et al.*, 2017; Asami and Nakagawa, 2018).

Soaking seeds in gibberellin (GA₃) 100 ppm has been reported to enhance growth speed, growth percentage, and seed viability in a variety of plants, including onion and shallot. However, despite its benefits, onion seeds are often of low quality, leading to slow and asynchronous germination. Given these challenges, an experiment was conducted to determine the most effective priming method and its impact on seed germination, aiming to achieve rapid and uniform seedling emergence.

Materials and Methods

The experiment investigated the effect of various treatments on onion seed germination and seedling growth.

Seed treatment and Experimental Design: Five treatments were implemented, including soaking seeds in 100 ppm of GA₃ for durations of 12, 18, and 24 hours, hydropriming (seeds soaked in water), and a control group. Each treatment was replicated four times, with 25 seeds in each replication. The experiment followed a Complete Randomized Block Design (CRD). After treatment, seeds were air-dried at room temperature until their original moisture content of 8% was achieved.

Germination Testing: Germination tests were conducted using the roll towel method in a germination room maintained at $25 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ and relative humidity of $90 \pm 3\%$. Germination percentage, seedling length, dry weight, and vigour index were determined on the 14th day. Dry weight measurements were obtained by oven-drying seedlings for two days at $85 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. The laboratory experiment was conducted from January to February 2024, at the analytical lab of the Department of Vegetable Science, Coimbatore. **Data Analysis:** Data entry and tabulation were performed using MS Excel, while statistical analysis was conducted using SPSS 16.0.

Results and Discussion:

The effect of different soaking durations of GA₃ on onion seed germination and seedling growth was investigated. The results are presented in Table 1.

Germination Percentage: Germination percentage increased with longer soaking durations of GA₃. Seeds soaked in GA₃ at 12 hours exhibited the highest germination percentage (88.54%), followed by 18 hours (84.38%) and 24 hours (79.81%). The control group (Fresh seeds), showed lower germination percentage (68.96%), indicating the effectiveness of GA₃ in promoting germination.

Shoot Length and Root Length: Similarly, shoot length and root length were positively influenced by GA₃ treatment. Seeds treated with GA₃ for 12 hours resulted in the longest shoot length (8.56 cm) and root length (7.09 cm) compared to other treatments. As soaking duration increased, shoot and root lengths slightly decreased, but remained higher than the control group.

Vigour Index: Vigour index, calculated based on seedling growth parameters, showed a similar trend. GA₃ treatment for 12 hours resulted in the highest vigour index I and II (1386.663 & 0.43), indicating strong seedling growth and vigor. The control group exhibited the lowest vigour index I and II (763.8175 & 0.16), suggesting weaker seedling development.

GA₃ plays a key role in breaking seed dormancy, promotes germination, increase the intermodal elongation and size by stimulating cell division in the cambial zone. Exogenous application (seed priming) of GA₃ increased the imbibition rate and increase the protein content in the aleurone layer by gene transcription factor and synthesis of hydrolyzing enzymes (α -amylase, proteases, glucanases, and phosphatases) occur which will break the food reserves (starch) into sucrose, it increase the cellular respiration (Holdsworth *et al.*, 2008) and stimulate the radicle protrusion from seeds which ultimately increase the germination percentage of the seeds (Mena *et al.*, 2002). The imbibition rate is mainly depends on the seed size and its chemical composition (Yudono, 2015). If the seed size is large, it contains more endosperm and it has ability to absorb more water.

The enhanced seed germination observed may be attributed to increased seedling vigor, elevated peroxide scavenging enzyme activities and reduced lipid peroxidation. Primed seeds often exhibit higher metabolic activity, facilitating efficient food mobilization during the early stages of germination. This increased metabolic results in increased shoot and root lengths (Brar *et al.*, 2019). Increased seedling vigor can be attributed to a combination of factors, including a higher respiration rate, increased metabolic activity and improved translocation of metabolites to

the growing point. A higher seedling vigor index indicates the seedlings' ability to thrive even under unfavorable conditions (Agung and Diara, 2017). Similar findings have been reported by various studies, including those conducted by Kumar and Singh (2013) in bitter melon, Vinayak *et al.* (2017) in ridge gourd and summer squash. GA₃ stimulates the dry matter accumulation in the seedling which was similar to the finding of Lokhande *et al.*, (2014) in onion.

Control seeds having low germination percentage and low seedling vigor index. This might be due to the fresh seeds having higher amount of auxin which reduce the plant growth. Higher amount auxins produce ethylene, which will inhibit the shoot and root growth ultimately seedling length will be reduced (Salisbury and Ross, 1992). Higher seedling vigor index regulates the uniform germination and produce healthier seedlings under wide range of stress condition (Agung and Diara, 2017).

The results obtained in this study are in line with previous research demonstrating the beneficial effects of GA₃ on seed germination and seedling growth. (Muruli, 2016; Thejawini *et al.*, 2018; Pokhrel *et al.*, 2019 ; Pangestuti *et al.*, 2021,).

Conclusion

In conclusion, soaking onion seeds in GA₃ at 100 ppm concentration for 12 hours significantly enhanced germination percentage, shoot and root length, and vigor index I and II over the control. These findings suggest that GA₃ treatment can be a valuable technique to improve onion seed germination and seedling growth, ultimately contributing to enhanced crop productivity.

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Table 1:Effect of of GA₃ on Seed Germination and Seedling Growth of onion var. Co (On) 6.

S.No	Treatment details	Germination percentage	Shoot length (cm)	Root length (cm)	Dry weight (mg)	Vigour Index I	Vigour index II
1	GA3 100ppm @12hrs	88.54	8.56	7.09	0.028	1386.663	0.43
2	GA3 100ppm @18hrs	84.38	8.16	6.36	0.024	1224.741	0.34
3	GA3 100ppm @24hrs	79.81	7.89	6.10	0.020	1117.46	0.29
4	Water	74.00	7.55	5.76	0.014	984.9121	0.25
5	Control	68.76	6.96	4.15	0.019	763.8175	0.16
	Mean	79.10	7.82	5.89	0.028	1095.519	0.29
	S.Ed	2.22	0.21	0.15	0.002	42.31	0.02
	CD (0.05%)	4.85	0.45	0.31	0.003	92.19	0.04